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PECULIARITIES OF THE INFLUENCE OF GLOBALIZATION AND DIGITALIZATION ON THE BANKING SYSTEM

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Abstract

The development of the banking sector is one of the important conditions for ensuring the sustainability of the economy, a factor of successful economic development and increasing the country's investment attractiveness. In recent years, banking activities under the influence of globalization and digitalization have been undergoing transformation due to the expansion and complication of banking products and services, the emergence of digital banks, the growth of competition between financial institutions and fintech companies, the increase in the volume of the financial market, the growth in the number of banking risks, the need to improve the quality of regulation and supervision, the need to develop common mechanisms for the transformation of both individual banks and the banking system as a whole, and others. All this leads to changes in approaches to the functioning of the banking sector. Previously traditional characteristics applicable to banking activities are being replaced by new ones due to the ongoing structural changes and the emergence of innovations, which contributes to the transformation of banks. Taking into account modern trends, the factors and mechanisms of formation of a competitive banking system should be determined, which in the conditions of transformation will allow the banking sector to strengthen its positions in the financial market.

Keywords: globalization, digitalization, banking sector, financial technologies, financial institution, risk.

Globalization and digitalization contribute to the emergence of fundamentally new economic ecosystems with a new business architecture of companies. At the same time, in most cases, the introduction of digital technologies depends on the objective historical basis for the development of the infrastructure of the state structure, traditions, and culture. [1]

The ongoing transformation of the global economy has also affected the financial system. The development of global capital markets is currently determined by a number of major factors, including the pace of technical and economic development, the level of liberalization of national capital markets, and the degree of political stability.

Globalization of banking activities, first of all, has led to the emergence of new institutions operating in the international banking market, increased competition, and the development of transnational banks. Under the influence of globalization, currently among the main trends in the development of the banking system, we can single out the merger of regional banking segments and their subsequent integration into a single world banking market. Significant consequences of

globalization have been the lowering of entry barriers to capital and the accelerated transition of financial institutions from specialization to universalization of their activities. In addition to expanding the customer base, this allowed banks to diversify risks and to be more competitive by flexibly responding to such features of the market environment as changing depositor behavior, shrinking margins, rising costs, development of information technology, identification of new sales channels, growing/changing customer requirements, new approaches to risk management, high capital requirements, fierce competition in the market, etc. [1]

It should be emphasized that in the context of the globalization of the economy and financial services, it is necessary to strengthen the regulatory mechanisms of the banking system, as capital flows between countries are increasing, and transnational companies, given the scale of their activities, can cause irreparable damage to the world economy. [2]

Experts at the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) attribute the accelerated development of digitalization to the emergence of new development vectors in the global economy. These

vectors only exacerbate risks, including cyberattacks, data theft/leakage, or fraud, infrastructure failures, and one of the main challenges of digitalization—the increase in misinformation. [3]

Digitalization of banking is changing the business processes of banking organizations, driven by the introduction of modern digital technologies in banking activities to meet the new demands of consumers for banking products and services. [4]

Competition and the need to take leading positions force companies to change their own economic and production models and transform and diversify existing business lines. Digitalization has facilitated a complete reform of almost all structural elements of credit institutions.

Modern banks are markedly different from their predecessors. Today, banks are at the center of digital innovation. They consider e-commerce business models, offer customers innovative products and services, participate in fintech partnerships and financing of innovative start-ups, contribute to the development of the digital market, the formation of a fair competitive space, the protection of user rights, and the growth of trust and cybersecurity. [1]

More innovation ultimately means more efficient new products and services that better meet customer needs, making it easier and more convenient for customers to interact with the bank. Innovation also helps companies make existing services better and more accessible.

It is important to note that as digitalization facilitates and encourages the emergence of new players in the banking system, ensuring fair competition among all market participants is of particular relevance. This issue is of paramount importance given all the risks (associated with the provision of banking services) and the quality of regulation and supervision. [5]

Integration of financial technologies and traditional banking organizations in the sphere of legal regulation often leads to certain conflicts. This happens for many reasons: first, fintech aims at decentralization,

which is associated with segmentation risks; Second, fintech products are complex services with financial characteristics and based on digital technologies; Third, fintech uses technologies such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, cloud computing - all of which can bring significant benefits to both banks and consumers, but at the same time are associated with significant risks. [4]

Over the last decade, the volume of assets of the global banking system increased almost 2.5 times; the capitalization of banks among the world's top 1000 banks exceeded USD 10 trillion; the share of financial system companies was 40% of the total value of profits of all Fortune Global 500 companies and the share of their assets was 74% of the total assets of all companies. The share of financial system companies was 40 percent of the total profit of all Fortune Global 500 companies, and the share of their assets was 74 percent of the total assets of all companies. At the same time, there has been a decline in the number of traditional banks and the share of their assets. One of the main reasons is the growth in the number of fintech companies, whose assets account for more than half of the global banking system, and whose growth rate has significantly exceeded that of traditional banking organizations. [6]

In fact, globalization and digitalization have influenced the emergence of new trends in the development of the world banking system, as well as new characteristics of banking activities, which have become a catalyst for increased competition not only between banks themselves, but also between banks and other financial institutions. This contributes to the emergence of new banking products and channels of interaction with customers, as well as the formation of entire ecosystems around financial institutions, which forces banks to use new methods of organizational management in order to ensure competitiveness in the market.

The trends in the development of the global banking system, the consequences of globalization and digitalization and new competitive factors are shown in table 1. [7]

Table 1.

Impact of globalization and digitalization on the banking system

1	Trends in the development of the world banking system	Expansion of the range and complexity of technologies of banking products and services; increasing competition between financial institutions and the tendency to deregulate their activities; the impact of technological revolutions on the development of the banking system; globalization and consolidation of banking activities, geographical expansion of financial institutions; increasing cost of financial resources and the desire to minimize the cost of banking products and services; general increase in the level of banking risks and the need to improve the quality of prudential supervision of financial institutions
2	Consequences of globalization and digitalization	Widening the difference in business size between large multinational and local banks; transition from a traditional bank (Bank 1.0) to a digital bank (Bank 4.0); blurring of boundaries between banking and non-banking products and services; of increasing role of synthesized products combining several products and services; increasing technological sophistication and complexity of risk management of banking systems; the need to increase the technological sophistication of the banking products and services offered; transition from paper-based information processing to digital information processing
3	New competitive factors	Internationalization including the penetration of foreign banks into local markets and fintech companies in the Internet space; opening of new capital markets, gradually transforming traditional deposit systems; diversification of banking activities; increasing segmentation of consumer groups; competition from para-banking organizations; development of systemic banking products and services; increasing influence of technology on banking activities and the emergence of banking ecosystems

Currently, the development of the banking system, taking into account various digital mechanisms and channels for the provision of banking products and services, is carried out in the following main directions:

- Creation of new ecosystems: inclusion of non-core enterprises previously non-core banks into a single ecosystem;
- Development of business architecture: introduction of digital technologies in the assessment of customer experience, creation of innovative products, value creation;
- strengthening the foundation: upgrading the technological base (e.g. flexible information infrastructure, cybersecurity, networking capabilities, big data and advanced analytics, comprehensive software), changing the corporate culture and organizational model. [1]

Undoubtedly, the development of globalization and digitalization will continue to have a significant impact on the transformation and development of the banking system, while the very functioning of the former banking system is under threat due to the rapidly increasing segmentation of the global economy.

Conclusion

Under the influence of globalization and digitalization, among the main trends in the development of the banking system are the following: merger of regional banking segments and formation of separate banking markets with their subsequent integration into a single global banking market; lowering of entry barriers to capital; transition of financial institutions from specialization to universalization of their activities; reforming of almost all structural elements of banks; increasing influence of fintech companies in the banking markets and emergence of services in their activities.

To meet modern standards, a traditional bank must organically integrate into the existing environment. In order for a bank to take a leading position in the market,

its activities should be based on a competent innovation policy and efficient use of resources/technologies in performing banking operations and providing services. At the same time, it is important to build ties with fintech companies and other institutions of the financial system in order to reduce costs, combine the strengths and features of partners and counterparties.

The experience of credit organizations and fintech companies has shown that, if properly built, banking ecosystems should proportionally combine financial banking products, advanced banking and non-banking services. At the same time, the ecosystem approach should not be seen as the final stage in a bank's digital transformation. In order to reduce the risks arising from digital transformation and globalization, as well as to achieve overall cumulative synergies, banks and fintech companies need to cooperate in organizing and implementing partnership programmes, as well as making investments, joint ventures and possible merger/acquisition procedures.

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